

The Relationship Between Tantrums And Social Intelligence In Kindergarten Children In Zarqa Governorate From The Perspective Of Mothers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 04, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: June 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Tantrums, Social Intelligence, Kindergarten Children.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4895102</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the relationship between tantrums and social intelligence in kindergarten children from the perspective of mothers. The study sample consisted of (106) mothers of kindergarten children aged (5-6) years from Zarqa Governorate, chosen by the intentional method. The correlational approach was followed. And to achieve the aim of the study, the researcher built and developed the first study tool related to tantrums in children and developed the second study tool related to social intelligence. The study results showed that the level of tantrums among kindergarten children from the mothers' point of view was moderate, and the results also showed that the level of social intelligence among kindergarten children from the mothers' point of view was moderate. The results also showed an inverse correlation between tantrums and social intelligence. Based on the study results, it recommended conducting more research and studies related to building appropriate programs to reduce tantrums in children and programs that help develop social intelligence.</i></p>

Introduction

Hassan (2015) emphasizes the importance of childhood, as it is the stage before the following stages, which impacts the life of the individual in the future, as it is the stage in which the child's personality, trends, tendencies, and characteristics are formed. For the individual to move to the next stage without disturbances, attention must be paid to this stage and the problems facing the child at this stage, including behavioral, psychological, emotional, and social problems and behavioral habits that affect the child. Psychologists have paid remarkable attention to the early childhood stage, as Freud mentioned the importance of this stage in shaping personality and linking the problems that occur with the individual with the disorders and problems that occurred to him in childhood and the role of parents at this stage. Anger is one of the behavioral problems facing parents and those around them, and it is difficult for them to deal with it. The problems facing the child have been classified into several categories. Al-Kafafi (2003) indicates that the problems in children and adolescents are multiple, and scholars rely on classifying problems either to the causes that lead to them or based on symptoms, and from classifications that depend on the causes and symptoms together. Tantrums have been classified within the behavioral social problems. Just as anger is one of the basic and innate emotions of the individual (fear - love - anger - sadness), so anger is an emotion that exists for all children and adults, regardless of the environmental and cultural differences between individuals, it is a global emotion, as is fear and happiness. It is not evidence of emotional instability, as it is one of the emotions that express feelings that are part of our daily life. (Abu Laban 2009).

Awad (2016) stresses the importance of parents' role in influencing the child and in the child's arrival to a state of emotional stability by taking care of the child from the side. And that the wrong methods of upbringing and the parents' lack of awareness of the importance of their role and their ignorance of correct practices in dealing with early childhood lead to emotional problems for the child. Al-Khader (2012) believes that anger, despite the benefits resulting from it in eliminating tension in the individual, has more negative consequences, as it negatively affects social relations and leads to the termination of social relations and the occurrence of alienation between individuals. Hence, the importance of social intelligence that develops as a result of the individual's interaction with the environment and those around him, and his influence with them, so that the child develops with the passage of time appropriate social communication skills and appropriate expressive and behavioral skills characterized by understanding others and being well-behaved in situations (Abdel Wahab, 2016).

The Study Problem

The study problem emerges through the results of the study of El-Desouki, Al-Beheiry (2015), which indicated the importance and role of social intelligence in reducing aggressive behavior, and the study of Ababneh (2012), which indicated the importance and role of social intelligence in reducing behavioral problems. Through previous studies, the existence of the problem of tantrums and their negative consequences

was found, and the importance of social intelligence in providing the child with social skills, and its effect in employing the child's skills in acceptably expressing emotions, and the role of social intelligence in reducing behavioral problems.

The study questions

The study problem is represented by the main question: What is the relationship between tantrums and social intelligence from the viewpoint of mothers in Zarqa Governorate?

Which is based on the following sub-questions:

1. What is the level of tantrums among kindergarten children?
2. What is the level of social intelligence among kindergarten children?
3. Is there a correlation between tantrums and social intelligence among kindergarten children?

The importance of the study

Theoretical importance

1. This study helps those responsible for children, including teachers and parents, to find smart and innovative ways to deal with them and reduce their anger levels.
2. The importance of the study is also based on the importance of social intelligence for the child, as a person is a social being that influences and is affected by others and teaches and learns from others.
3. This study enriches the Arab and Jordanian libraries because of their importance in proper child-rearing methods in dealing with anger.
4. Shed light on new studies dealing with the anger variable and how to deal with it.

Applied importance

1. This study helps teachers in dealing with children who suffer from tantrums and the role of the environment in controlling the child's anger and feelings.
2. This study contributes to the awareness of parents and caregivers of children of the importance of family upbringing and education in every behavior carried out by the child.
3. The study contributes to providing a picture of tantrums in children and that researchers conduct research that helps study ways to deal with tantrums.
4. Shedding light on the relationship between tantrums and social intelligence, and thus carrying out studies that help search for ways and methods that help develop the growth of social intelligence.
5. It helps in motivating researchers to conduct new research by reviewing what has been reached through the results and recommendations.

The limits of the study

Objective limits

This study was limited to investigating the relationship between tantrums and social intelligence from the viewpoint of mothers in Zarqa Governorate.

Human limits: The study was applied to a sample of mothers of children from the second stage, whose ages range between (5-6) years.

Spatial limits: This study was applied in governmental and private schools in Zarqa Governorate.

Temporal limits: The study is conducted in the second semester (2019-2020).

Terminology of study

temper tantrums

Salk (2020) defines a tantrum as: It is a violent emotional outburst that may be a response to a child's feeling of frustration. Its causes include fatigue, hunger, the need for attention, and it may be the child's mood and personality; in rare cases, a psychological or social disorder may cause it, and this is more likely if the anger continues to repeat during the same day.

Social Intelligence

Gardner defines it as the ability to understand the feelings and emotional states, distinguish between them, know their motivations, ability to distinguish non-verbal signs and gestures, and the ability to interact effectively with others (Al-Khazraji, Al-Ezzi, 2010).

Kindergarten children

Bahadur (2011) defines the kindergarten child: The child in the age group extending from (4-6) years. Some have called this stage the term early childhood.

Previous Studies

Ala Al-Din and Al-Hih's (2018) study aimed to reveal the effect of a collective counseling program in reducing symptoms of anger among a sample of female Syrian refugee children living in Jordan. The study sample consisted of (32) girls whose ages ranged between (10-13) years; the results of the study indicated that there are statistically significant differences at a level between the mean scores of the experimental group and the scores of the control group on the scale of anger with its six dimensions: Anger triggers, feelings associated

with anger, psychosomatic symptoms, subjective and external anger, and unity of anger, in the post-measurement in favor of the experimental group.

The study of Khawaldeh, Makanin (2018) aimed to measure the effectiveness of anger management training in reducing aggressive behavior and improving psychological resilience. Where the sample consisted of (22) children from Amman, which was divided into two control and experimental groups, the experimental group underwent an experimental program consisting of nine sessions for eight weeks. A scale of aggressive behavior and psychological flexibility before and after implementing the program was applied to the participants in both groups. The study results indicated the effectiveness of anger management training in reducing aggressive behavior and improving the psychological flexibility of children with hearing impairment. The study of Al-Jarrah, Asla (2016), aimed to reveal the level of social intelligence and strategies for conflict management of ordinary students and problem behavior in the secondary stage. The study sample consisted of (439) male and female students; the sample was chosen by a random cluster method from high school students in the Galilee region in Palestine and achieved the study's objectives. The two researchers codified the Sternberg scale for social intelligence and the Ting-Tome scale for conflict management strategies; the results of the study showed that the level of social intelligence was high for both ordinary students and those with problem behavior and that the strategy and integration strategy was more used by ordinary students and those with problem behavior. While the neglect strategy was less used for them, the results also showed no statistically significant differences in the level of social intelligence.

The study of El-Desouki, Al-Buhairi, and Abdullah (2015) aimed to uncover the relationship between social intelligence and aggressive behavior. The sample consisted of (60) male and female students, whose ages ranged between (11-12) years.

The study (Ali, 2015) aimed at knowing the level of social intelligence among kindergarten children. The study sample consisted of (100) children and girls from (10) kindergartens, and they were distributed according to the variables of sex and academic achievement of the father and mother belonging to the Directorate of Education of Rusafa First and Second in Baghdad, the Social Intelligence Scale (2010) was used for the Iraqi environment for children aged six years. The results of the study indicated an advanced growth in the social intelligence scores of the research sample, as it came with an arithmetic average greater than the hypothetical average of the scale. Statistically, significant differences were found between the averages of social intelligence scores among kindergarten children according to the gender variable. In favor of males, while there is no effect on the social intelligence variable according to the father's achievement, on the contrary, there is an effect on the social intelligence according to the mother's academic achievement variable.

The study of Alkafash (2015) aimed to identify the social intelligence of children aged six years and for the pre-school grade. The researcher used the social intelligence test for the Iraqi environment; the sample consisted of (100) children and girls from (10) kindergartens; the results of the study showed an advanced growth in social intelligence scores, as it came with an arithmetic average greater than the hypothetical average. There are statistically significant differences between the average scores of social intelligence among kindergarten children according to the gender variable and in favor of males.

The study of Solvain (2017) aimed to reveal the feelings associated with the approach, the perseverance of young children, and the negative reactions to failure, and the study sample consisted of (87) children of (5) months old. The study used classification of mothers' behaviors, whereby mothers reported infant moods, as well as the incidence of anger and tantrums, the effect of mothers' anger, was also discovered, as the relationship was positive, the more angered the mother acted, the more negative reactions appeared in the children.

Mazdumes & Barens (2013) study aimed to answer the following question: Is child care in pre-school centers associated with tantrums and unmanageable behavior over time until entering school? The study sample consisted of (1201) children, distributed between the ages of (30-51) months. The study used the Individual Developmental Model Test to test the relationship between early childhood care experiences and challenging behavior. The results showed higher complex moods and lower verbal ability of the children attending these centers, the results indicate that early exposure to care at the center, before reaching the age of two years, is a risk factor for subsequent behavior problems, especially when the child is in it for a long time.

The study (Dilick & Novak, 2011) aimed to uncover emotional and social intelligence and empathy as predictors of narcissism, and it also aimed to link narcissism with social intelligence and emotional intelligence. The study sample consisted of (306) individuals whose ages ranged between (19-26) years of whom (242) females and (64) males. The results of the study showed a positive correlation between narcissism, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence. The results also showed a negative relationship between narcissism and empathy.

The study (Belden & Thomson & Lubi, 2008) aimed to reveal the behavioral differences in tantrums among children who suffer from mood disorders and health in pre-school. The study sample consisted of (279)

pre-school children. The study used non-parametric analyzes to examine the characteristics of tantrums in children (intensity, frequency, context, and ability to recover). The results showed that pre-school children who suffer from tantrums are more destructive and violent than depressed and unhealthy groups. In addition, depressed pre-school children were more aggressive towards other things and people than healthy children. Finally, the study showed that behaviorally depressed children show more self-damaging tantrums than children from healthy and disruptive groups.

Rice's (2006) study aimed to determine the effects of using different types of anger expression; its purpose was to show differences in the characteristics of anger among children, whose data indicated that the characteristics of anger are between high, medium, and low. The study sample consisted of (1060) students from the sixth grade who were known to persistent anger under any stimulus and who possessed patterns of expressing anger through the data of each one of them; the results indicated that reflection or control of anger is more effective in anger attack and in reducing the tantrum of schoolchildren.

Study Approach

This study relied on the correlational approach to measure the correlational relationship between the study variables represented in the study variables. Accordingly, the study relied on the theoretical method that relies on data by referring to previous studies related to tantrums and social intelligence through books, references, related articles, and published research to form the study's theoretical framework through the collection of primary data. This part comes to cover aspects of the study, through which the study questions will be answered and verified by distributing a tool to the study sample, developing it, and analyzing it.

The study population

The study population consisted of mothers, children, and kindergartens in Zarqa Governorate.

The study sample

The study members consisted of mothers of kindergarten children in Zarqa Governorate, who were chosen by the easy intentional method, as the number reached (106) mothers of kindergarten children, (170) tools were distributed for each of the two variables, 106 questionnaires from the anger variable questionnaires were answered, and 106 social intelligence questionnaires were answered.

The study tools

To achieve the objectives of the current study, two tools were relied upon: the Tantrums Tool and the Social Intelligence Tool, and below is an explanation of how to prepare them.

First: set up the tantrums tool.

The first study tool related to tantrums was built and designed by: Forming a survey question (open questionnaire) for the opinions of mothers of kindergarten children, which is found in Appendix (4), and all the mothers' opinions about the manifestations of tantrums in their children were taken into consideration, where the most important answers emerged, including - breaking and sabotaging anything around the child while he was entering a fit of anger - sabotaging his clothes - screaming loudly. The researcher prepared a list of the tool in its initial form, which is found in Appendix (5), and presented it to the arbitrators specialized in the field of education and psychology from inside and outside Al-Isra University of (10) arbitrators and the appendix (10). Two paragraphs were deleted from the paragraphs of the tool, namely: fabricating problems and hitting children around him because of the presence of paragraphs that include problems and beating, and modifying the wording of some paragraphs sabotaging his clothes to ruining his clothes to become more appropriate and belonging to the tool. Based on the modifications, the tool was finalized.

Tool validity:

The validity of the tool was verified through its apparent validity and constructive validity.

Virtual validity

It is the validity that depends on the preliminary examination of the tool's content, the appropriateness of the articles of the tool, and the linguistic integrity, through the help of specialists in the field, and that the agreed percentage is more than (75%). To ensure the apparent authenticity of the tool, the researcher presented the tool in its initial form to a group of arbitrators specialized in education, psychology, and childhood, and their number reached (10) arbitrators. They were asked to express their observations and opinions on the areas of the tool in terms of the soundness of the phrasing of its paragraphs and their belonging to the field in which they were placed, the clarity of the meaning of the paragraph, and any necessary notes or amendments that would work to bring out the study tool in an appropriate form in its final form, as the language wording was modified and two paragraphs of the tool's paragraphs were deleted because they did not belong to the field.

Constructive validity

It means the consistency of all the paragraphs of the tool to which they belong, which is that the paragraphs measure what they have been put to measure.

Table (1) below shows the correlation coefficients between each paragraph and the overall score for the anger tool, and it represents its validity coefficients.

Table 1: The correlation coefficient of the paragraph mark to the overall score of the anger tool

Paragraph number	Paragraph phrase	Correlation coefficient
1	Cries loudly	.680
2	He sits alone, separated from others	.416
3	Be silent	.397
4	Strongly shouts	.423
5	He uses violence to get what he wants	.593
6	He raises his voice while talking	.429
7	Resist others	.599
8	He closes his ears	.783
9	Sticking his teeth	.665
10	Feel the urge to vomit	.551
11	Flops with random movements	.505
12	Quarrels with the cause of anger	.445
13	Tear off clothes	.547
14	He hits his head against the wall and the floor	.597
15	Uses profanity	.748
16	He is scratching his face	.605
17	Closes doors forcefully and aggressively	.504
18	He murmurs and speaks in a low voice	.444
19	Cracking what he finds in front of him	.680
20	Vandalize the property	.781
21	The door closes on himself	.441

The correlation coefficient is statistically significant at a level of significance (0.05).

It is evident from Table (1) above that all the parameters of the paragraph marks of the anger tool with the total score of the tool are statistically significant at a level, which indicates its empirical validity.

Second: Preparing the social intelligence tool

The second study tool related to social intelligence was developed by following the following steps: Review the theoretical literature and benefit from previous studies such as the study of the Alalem (2018), the study of Al-Khazraji and Al-Izzi (2010), the study of Abd al-Wahhab and Abdullah (2016) and the study of Al-Jarrah and Asla (2016) and refer to the book on emotional and social intelligence of the kindergarten child, Kafafi, Al-Nayal, Salem (2008).

In light of this, the researcher drafted the tool in its preliminary form, Appendix (2), and presented it to the arbitrators specialized in the field of education and psychology, who numbered (10) arbitrators in Appendix (8).

The opinions of the referee's committee were taken to achieve the objectives of the study. Six paragraphs were added to the second study tool, which is as follows:

1. He can know the feelings of others.
2. He can solve a problem with his friend through dialogue.
3. He likes to be an active member of a group.
4. Lend a helping hand to his friend if he gets stuck.
5. Likes to take the opinions of others.
6. Friends share positive experiences.
7. Sympathizes with others.

Paragraph No. (8) has been amended from (who can control his negative emotions) to (can control his emotions). Paragraph No. (7) has been amended from (He can adapt to new situations) to (Has the skill of dealing with adaptation to new situations), and paragraph No. (9) of (builds and develops his personality and learns from the situations he is exposed to) has been amended, based on the modifications, the tool was finalized, Annex (3).

Tool validity

The validity of the tool was verified through its apparent validity and constructive validity.

Apparent validity

It is the validity that depends on the preliminary examination of the tool's content, the appropriateness of the articles of the tool, and the linguistic integrity, through the help of specialists in the field, and that the agreed percentage is more than (75%). And to ensure the apparent validity of the tool, the researcher presented the tool in its initial form to a group of arbitrators specialized in education, psychology, and childhood, and their number reached (10) arbitrators. Appendix (8) shows that. They were asked to express their observations and opinions on the areas of the tool in terms of the soundness of the phrasing of its paragraphs and their belonging to the field in which they were placed, and the clarity of the meaning of the paragraph and any notes or necessary amendments that would work to produce the study tool in an appropriate form in its final form, as the language wording was modified and (6) paragraphs of the questionnaire were added.

Constructive validity

It means the consistency of all the paragraphs of the tool to which they belong, which is that the paragraphs measure what they have been put to measure. Table (2) below shows the correlation coefficients between each paragraph and the overall score of the social intelligence tool, which represents its validity coefficients.

Table 2: Paragraph score correlation coefficient with the overall score of the Social Intelligence Tool

Paragraph number	Paragraph phrase	Correlation coefficient
1	Possesses the skill of resolving disputes with his friends	.589
2	Provides help to others	.451
3	Has the skill to correct the mistakes of others	.682
4	He looks at life with optimism	.413
5	He bears his failure in a specific task and works to correct errors	.689
6	Treat others kindly	.671
7	Possesses coping skills to adapt to new situations	.447
8	He can control his emotions	.544
9	He learns from the situations he is exposed to	.398
10	He resolves disputes among his friends	.709
11	He feels happy for his friend's success	.536
12	Easily make friends	.445
13	Cares about the feelings of others	.446
14	He has the leadership skill	.628
15	Accept disagreement with others	.587
16	Loves to communicate with others	.398
17	He expresses his feelings clearly	.449
18	They love dealing with new things	.504
19	He feels happy in the presence of others	.508
20	Shows a sense of humor and fun with others	.456
21	Learn from other people's experiences	.608
22	He can control his emotions	.520
23	Forgive others if they sinned with him	.453
24	He bears the responsibility for the tasks assigned to him	.398
25	He loves teamwork	.516
26	Blends easily with the surrounding environment	.522
27	Can know the feelings of others (sadness, happiness, anger)	.692
28	He can solve a problem with his friend through dialogue	.511
29	He likes to be an active member of a group	.412
30	He offers a helping hand to his friend if he encounters a problem	.527
31	He loves taking the opinions of others	.455
32	Friends share positive experiences	.443
33	Sympathizes with others	.415

* Correlation coefficient is statistically significant at (0.05) level

It is evident from the above table (2) that all the parameters of the scores of the paragraphs of the social intelligence tool with the overall score of the tool are statistically significant at a level, which indicates its experimental validity.

Reliability of the study tools

To ensure the reliability of the study tools, the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency factor was calculated;. However, the rules for measuring the value to be obtained are not specified, the value of alpha is considered from the application point of view for administrative and human sciences in general, and it is considered acceptable. The values of the reliability coefficient for the main content of the tool ranged between (0.85) and (0.79), as these values are acceptable for this study, and the following table No. (3) shows the results of the reliability of this study. Also, to ensure the tool's stability, the repetition method was used, whereby the items of the tool were redistributed to individuals twice with a time difference of (14) days under conditions similar to the first application, and the stability factor was calculated. Table (3) shows the stability coefficients.

Table 3: The coefficients of the two tools of anger and social intelligence by the Cronbach-alpha and

Tool	Reliability coefficients	
	Cronbach-alpha method	Return method (Pearson Correlation Coefficient)
Anger tool	0.82	0.85
Social intelligence tool	0.79	0.81

repetition

methods

Determine the levels of the answer

The researcher used the Likert / Five Point Scale to assess the answers of mothers of children to each of the two tools of anger and social intelligence by placing a sign (x) for the answer that reflects the degree of their agreement, whether (never, rarely, sometimes, often, always) in order to estimate the level of the answer on the fields of study from the point of view of kindergarten mothers, and three levels of arithmetic averages have been adopted as follows:

- From 1-2.33 low approval score.
- From 2.34-3.66 score / intermediate approval
- From 3.67 to 5 high approval score.

Where the limits of the level were calculated as follows:

$$1.33 = (\text{Lower Class} - \text{Highest Class}) / 3$$

First: The results related to the first question, which states: What is the level of tantrums among kindergarten children from the viewpoint of mothers?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means, standard deviation, relative weight, and level of the respondents' responses to each paragraph of the anger tool were calculated, and Table (4) illustrates this.

Table 4: The arithmetic average, standard deviation, relative weight, and degree of agreement for the study sample responses to the Tantrums tool

Paragraph number	Rank	Paragraph phrase	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Relative weight	Level
13	1	Damaging his clothes	4.44	.70	88.87	High
14	2	He hits his head against the wall and the floor	4.30	.86	86.04	High
11	3	Flops with random movements	3.94	.93	78.87	High
10	4	Feel the urge to vomit	3.90	.89	77.92	High
16	5	He is scratching his face	3.78	1.05	75.66	High
20	6	Vandalize the property	3.71	1.00	74.15	High
8	7	He closes his ears	3.66	1.16	73.21	Average
15	8	Uses profanity	3.65	1.12	73.02	Average
19	9	Cracking what he finds in front of him	3.64	1.10	72.83	Average

Paragraph number	Rank	Paragraph phrase	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Relative weight	Level
9	10	Sticking his teeth	3.59	1.33	71.89	Average
2	11	He sits alone, separated from others	3.46	.92	69.25	Average
17	12	He closes the doors aggressively	3.46	.97	69.25	Average
4	13	Strongly shouts	3.38	1.01	67.55	Average
12	14	Quarreled with reasoned anger	3.12	1.07	62.45	Average
21	15	He closes the door on himself	3.11	.90	62.26	Average
18	16	He murmurs and speaks in a low voice	2.80	1.12	56.04	Average
5	17	He uses violence to get what he wants	2.72	1.19	54.34	Average
6	18	He raises his voice while talking	2.68	1.03	53.58	Average
3	19	Remain silent	2.60	1.07	52.08	Average
7	20	Resist others	2.43	.94	48.68	Average
1	21	Cries loudly	1.68	.80	33.58	Low
		The total score	3.34	.85	66.74	Average

It is noticed from Table (4) the values of the arithmetic averages and the standard deviation for the paragraphs of the Tantrum Tool, that the level of the tantrums was moderate, the arithmetic average reached (3.34) and represents the relative weight (66.74), and the arithmetic averages range between (4.44-1.68), as the thirteenth paragraph "damaging his clothes" ranked first with an arithmetic averages (4.44) and a relative weight (88.87) and the researcher attributes this result to the fact that the child at this stage has developed different ways of expressing anger, so that his ability to destroy his clothes is the fastest method, the researcher attributes this result to the fact that the child at this stage has developed different ways of expressing anger, so that his ability to destroy his clothes is the fastest method of immediate emotional discharge, and it is a method that draws the attention of those around him and considers clothes as his personal possessions that he can dispose of. This stage is characterized by intense emotion and fluctuations in the emotional aspect. While the first paragraph got crying loudly, ranked last with an arithmetic average (1.68) and relative weight (33.58). The researcher attributes the reason to the social upbringing that limits the style of crying among children at this stage, as behaviors linked to the stage of breastfeeding, so the child resorts to expressing behaviors that diverge from likening him to a small child, as parents use phrases such as Do not cry like a little boy you are grown up. Also one of the reasons is that as the child grows, the ways of expressing tantrums change.

Second: The results related to the second question, which he stated: What is the level of social intelligence among kindergarten children from the viewpoint of mothers?

To answer this question, the arithmetic average, standard deviation, relative weight, and level of the responses of the sample members on each paragraph of the social intelligence tool were calculated, and Table (5) illustrates this.

Table 5: The arithmetic average, standard deviation, relative weight, and degree of agreement for the study sample responses to the social intelligence tool

Paragraph number	Rank	Paragraph phrase	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Relative weight	Level
3	1	Has the skill to correct errors	3.05	1.09	60.94	Average
32	2	Friends share positive experiences	2.96	1.18	59.25	Average
8	3	He can control his emotions	2.95	1.07	59.06	Average
31	4	He loves taking the opinions of others	2.94	1.20	58.87	Average
30	5	Offer a helping hand to his friend if he encountered a problem	2.88	1.31	57.55	Average
5	6	Bear his failure in a specific task and works to correct errors	2.87	.83	57.36	Average
29	7	He likes to be an active member of a group	2.85	1.23	56.98	Average
17	8	He expresses his feelings clearly	2.84	1.33	56.79	Average
18	9	He loves dealing with new things	2.82	1.48	56.42	Average

Paragraph number	Rank	Paragraph phrase	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Relative weight	Level
33	10	Sympathizes with others	2.81	1.20	56.23	Average
13	11	Cares about the feelings of others	2.76	1.28	55.28	Average
20	12	Shows a sense of humor and fun with others	2.76	1.37	55.28	Average
22	13	He can control his emotions	2.76	1.00	55.28	Average
25	14	He loves teamwork	2.76	1.41	55.28	Average
19	15	He feels happy in the presence of others	2.75	1.37	54.91	Average
28	16	He can solve a problem with his friend through dialogue.	2.75	.83	54.91	Average
9	17	He learns from the situations he is exposed to	2.69	1.32	53.77	Average
16	18	Loves to communicate with others	2.66	1.47	53.21	Average
26	19	Blends easily with the surrounding environment	2.61	1.42	52.26	Average
24	20	He bears the responsibility for the tasks assigned to him	2.58	1.36	51.70	Average
14	21	He has the leadership skill	2.53	1.11	50.57	Average
7	22	Possesses coping skills to adapt to new situations	2.52	1.01	50.38	Average
23	23	Forgive others if they sinned with him	2.52	1.46	50.38	Average
2	24	Provides help to others	2.49	.89	49.81	Average
12	25	Easily make friends	2.46	1.24	49.25	Average
15	26	Accept disagreement with others	2.46	.82	49.25	Average
4	27	He looks at life with optimism	2.42	.86	48.49	Average
10	28	He resolves disputes among his friends	2.40	1.00	47.92	Average
6	29	Treat others kindly	2.39	.99	47.74	Average
1	30	He has the skill of resolving disputes with his friends	2.37	1.04	47.36	Average
21	31	Learn from other people's experiences	2.37	1.12	47.36	Average
11	32	He feels happy about his friend's success	2.28	.94	45.66	Low
27	33	He can know the feelings of others	2.14	.86	42.83	Low
		The total score	2.65	.89	52.98	Average

It is noticed from Table (5) the values of the arithmetic means and the standard deviation for the paragraphs of the social intelligence tool that the level of social intelligence came with a moderate degree, the arithmetic average is (2.65), and the relative weight is (52.98), and the arithmetic averages range between (3.05-2.14). The third paragraph, which possesses the skill of correcting errors, ranked first, with an arithmetic average (3.05) and a relative weight (60.94). The researcher attributes the result that the child has a level of social intelligence, correct mistakes, correct discrimination from error, and correct errors. Through socialization, parents often develop in the child how to correct mistakes and reinforce this behavior. At the same time, the twenty-seventh paragraph (he can know the feelings of others) ranked last, with an arithmetic average (2.14) and a relative weight (42.83).The researcher attributes the reason to the overlapping and diversity of feelings and the mood swings that occur in others that lead to the difficulty of distinguishing the child for these feelings, and the researcher also attributes the result to the difference in mothers' perception of others' feelings and their effect on the child's perception of others' feelings.

Third: The results related to the third question, which states: Is there a correlation between tantrums and social intelligence among kindergarten children?

To answer this question, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between the marks of mothers' answers to the anger and social intelligence questionnaires, as shown in Table (6) below.

Table 6: Pearson correlation coefficient between the marks of mothers' answers to the two tools of anger and social intelligence	Statistical significance
Correlation coefficient value	
-.225*	.021

It is evident from the above Table that the value of the correlation coefficient between tantrums and social intelligence (- 0.225), which is negative and a statistically function at a level of significance, and this means that the higher the level of social intelligence in children, the fewer tantrums they have, and vice versa.

The researcher attributes the result that whenever the child possesses social intelligence, he is characterized by self-control and the ability to perceive the situation and the consequences of his behavior. He knows the effect of his behavior resulting from anger on others, while a child who has a high level of tantrums, his level of social intelligence decreases due to his inability to perceive and distinguish the effect of his behavior on others, and this is what the study of Al-Dessouk et al. (2015) and the study of Ababneh (2012) showed.

Discussion of the study results

The results related to the first question showed that the degree of level of tantrums among the kindergarten children was moderate. The results related to the second question also showed that the level of social intelligence among kindergarten children was of moderate degree; concerning the third question. It was found that the inverse relationship between tantrums and social intelligence, and this result was similar to the conclusion reached by El-Desouki and others (2015), with the existence of a negative statistically significant relationship between social intelligence and aggressive behavior. While it disagreed with the Asalah study (2016), which found a higher level of social intelligence for students with problem behavior, while the current study showed that children who have tantrums, their social intelligence decreases as the level of anger increases. It was similar to the findings of Ababneh's study (2012) regarding the existence of an inverse relationship between social intelligence and behavioral problems.

Concerning the first question related to the level of tantrums, the results of the current study are consistent with the results of the Rice study (Raice, 2006), which found that there are levels of anger behaviors between high, medium, and low. The results of the level of anger differed with the study of Potegel & Davidson (Potegel & Davidson, 2003), as the level of anger was low in the sample, while the results of the current study showed the level of anger was moderate. The results of the current study regarding the second question differed from the findings of the study of Ali (2015) and the alkhafash study (2015), as the level of social intelligence among students with problem behavior was high, which is the opposite of the result of the current research, which indicates that the level of social intelligence was moderate.

Conclusions

In light of the results of the current study, the researcher reached the following conclusions:

1. The results showed that the level of tantrums in children was average from the mothers' point of view.
2. The results showed that the level of social intelligence among children, from the viewpoint of mothers, is average.

3. There is an inverse relationship between tantrums in children and their social intelligence, as the higher the child's tantrums, the lower the level of social intelligence and vice versa.

Study Recommendations

In light of the results of the study, the study recommends the following:

1. Preparing programs to help the kindergarten teacher in ways of developing social intelligence.
2. Train teachers in kindergarten on programs that help children deal with tantrums
3. Hold training courses and workshops for mothers in schools and community centers that include axes of refinement of emotions in children.
4. Hold training courses and workshops for mothers in schools and community centers that include methods of developing social intelligence in children through daily life.
5. Conduct more educational research that includes building programs to help children control anger.
6. Conduct more educational research on children's tantrums and link them to some variables (gender, educational level).
7. Conduct more research that includes social intelligence and linking it to some variables such as the educational level of parents/gender.
8. Conduct more research that includes social intelligence and its link to methods of socialization.

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